

Supplementary Material

S1 Validation of the LBM solver against analytical solutions

To ensure the hydrodynamic reliability of the lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) solver for subsequent complex pore simulations, it is validated through a generalized Couette flow benchmark test. The LBM solver employs the D3Q19 discrete velocity model coupled with a single-relaxation-time (SRT) collision operator. Solid boundaries are treated via the half-way bounce-back scheme, and volumetric forces are incorporated using the Guo forcing scheme. Detailed algorithmic parameters and convergence criteria are summarized in [Table S1](#).

Table S1 LBM computational parameters configured for hydrodynamic validations.

Parameter	Setting
Dimensionless relaxation time, τ_r	1.0
Lattice spacing, Δx	1.0
Lattice time step, Δt	1.0
Lattice driving acceleration, a	1.00×10^{-3}
Lattice discrete model	D3Q19
Collision operator	Single Relaxation Time (SRT)
Forcing scheme	Guo's scheme
Solid boundary condition	Half-way bounce-back
Convergence criterion 1	Global relative error
Convergence criterion 2	Maximum Mach number limit
Convergence criterion 3	Steady-state mass flux curve

The generalized Couette flow validation simulates the steady-state Newtonian flow between two parallel plates. The top boundary moves at a constant velocity (U), while the flow field is concurrently driven by various dimensionless pressure gradients

(B). As illustrated in Fig. S1, the LBM-simulated dimensionless velocity profiles (u_x/U) across the normalized height (y/h) match well with the analytical Navier-Stokes solutions under varying gradients (where u_x and h denote the local flow velocity and plate spacing, respectively). This mathematical agreement verifies the solver's accuracy in capturing fundamental momentum transfer and complex boundary conditions.

Fig. S1 Comparison of velocity profiles between the LBM solutions and analytical solutions for generalized Couette flow under various pressure gradients (B).

S2 Validation of grid convergence for CT-reconstructed models

In Micro-CT-based pore-scale simulations, spatial resolution directly dictates the geometric fidelity and the accuracy of computed intrinsic permeability. Accordingly, a grid convergence assessment is performed using a standard Sandstone S9 core to determine the optimal balance between computational precision and efficiency. The 3D digital model ($300 \times 300 \times 300$ voxels) is sourced from the public micro-porous media

database at Imperial College London. Its testing permeability, serving as the validation benchmark, is 2735 mD (Dong 2007).

Fig. S2 Evolution of the staircase effect on the solid-fluid boundaries within a local 2D cross-section under different grid resolutions: (a) 12×12 grids (sampling rate = 5); (b) 30×30 grids (sampling rate = 2); (c) 40×40 grids (sampling rate = 1.5); (d) 60×60 grids (sampling rate = 1); (e) 80×80 grids (sampling rate = 0.75); and (f) 120×120 grids (sampling rate = 0.5). Note that these images represent a zoomed-in sub-region ($1/5$ of the overall domain length) extracted from the 3D digital rock models.

By adjusting the sampling rate during image reconstruction, a series of digital core models with voxel resolutions ranging from $60 \times 60 \times 60$ to $600 \times 600 \times 600$ are generated. To visualize the mitigation of the staircase effect at the solid-liquid boundaries via grid refinement, Fig. S2 presents a magnified 2D slice. The evaluation results (Table S2) indicate that excessively coarse grids (e.g., a sampling rate of 5) fail to resolve fine pore throats, severely distorting the computed permeability (relative error: -99.53%). With increasing grid density, the computed permeability progressively converges. At the original resolution (sampling rate = 1), the solution achieves grid convergence, restricting the relative error against the benchmark to within 5% (-4.42%). Consequently, all MSW specimens investigated in the main text maintain their original CT resolutions to ensure topological fidelity and computational reliability.

Table S2 Computed permeabilities and relative errors under varying grid resolutions.

Sampling factor	Lattice dimensions ($N_x \times N_y \times N_z$)	Computed permeability (mD)	Relative error (%)
5	$60 \times 60 \times 60$	1.295×10^1	-99.53
2	$150 \times 150 \times 150$	4.010×10^3	46.62
1.5	$200 \times 200 \times 200$	2.243×10^3	-17.99
1	$300 \times 300 \times 300$	2.614×10^3	-4.42
0.75	$400 \times 400 \times 400$	2.631×10^3	-3.80
0.5	$600 \times 600 \times 600$	2.724×10^3	-0.40

S3 Validation of intrinsic permeability for diverse 3D porous media

To address highly heterogeneous and anisotropic materials, this section further validates the solver's accuracy in computing intrinsic permeability within complex 3D

pore spaces. The validation incorporates six types of porous media with varying porosities and mean pore sizes, ranging from relatively regular sphere packings (SandPack series and Synthetic silica A1) to natural digital cores with highly complex pore structures (Berea sandstone, Fontainebleau sandstone S9, and Grosmont carbonate C1). These 3D digital models were obtained from the Imperial College London public dataset, with corresponding laboratory-measured reference permeabilities sourced from [Dong \(2007\)](#). The intrinsic permeabilities of these media were computed independently along three orthogonal directions. Compared to the reference values ([Table S3](#)), the computational errors of the LBM solver are constrained to within 10% in most cases. This confirms the solver's robustness in simulating flow through real porous media with complex topologies and connectivities.

Table S3 Validation of LBM-simulated permeabilities against reference data.

Flow direction	Sample	Porosity (%)	Average pore diameter (mm)	Reference permeability, k_{ref} (mD)	Simulated permeability, k_{sim} (mD)	Relative error (%)
x	SandPack F42A	32.21%	0.113301	/	59090	/
	SandPack LV60A	36.31%	0.072363	/	36700	/
	Synthetic silica A1	42.87%	0.033113	8272	8240	-0.39
	Berea sandstone	19.65%	0.041493	1360	1247	-8.31
	Sandstone S9	22.17%	0.064737	2735	2629	-3.88
	Carbonate C1	23.26%	0.039855	785	736	-6.24

y	SandPack F42A	32.21%	0.113301	/	57240	/
	SandPack LV60A	36.31%	0.072363	/	32850	/
	Synthetic silica A1	42.87%	0.033113	7977	7744	-2.92
	Berea sandstone	19.65%	0.041493	1304	1125	-13.73
	Sandstone S9	22.17%	0.064737	2093	2086	-0.33
	Carbonate C1	23.26%	0.039855	1469	1520	3.47
z	SandPack F42A	32.21%	0.113301	/	58950	/
	SandPack LV60A	36.31%	0.072363	/	31280	/
	Synthetic silica A1	42.87%	0.033113	5412	5308	-1.92
	Berea sandstone	19.65%	0.041493	1193	1053	-11.74
	Sandstone S9	22.17%	0.064737	1844	1919	4.07
	Carbonate C1	23.26%	0.039855	1053	961	-8.74
Average	SandPack F42A	32.21%	0.113301	59000	58430	-0.97
	SandPack LV60A	36.31%	0.072363	35300	33610	-4.79
	Synthetic silica A1	42.87%	0.033113	7220	7097	-1.70
	Berea sandstone	19.65%	0.041493	1286	1142	-11.20
	Sandstone S9	22.17%	0.064737	2224	2211	-0.58
	Carbonate	23.26%	0.039855	1102	1072	-2.72

References

Dong, H. 2007. Micro-CT imaging and pore network extraction. Ph.D. thesis, Imperial College London, London, UK.

Imperial College London. 2007. Micro-CT images of sandstones, carbonates, sand-packs, synthetic silica and their extracted networks. Department of Earth Science and Engineering. Available at: <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/earth-science/research/research-groups/pore-scale-modelling/micro-ct-images-and-networks/>.